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The Effect of Socio-Economic Factors on Property Tax Revenues: Evidence From Türkiye Sosyo-Ekonomik Faktörlerin Emlak Vergisi Gelirleri Üzerindeki Etkisi: Türkiye'den Kanıtlar

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effects of socio-economic factors on property tax revenues in Türkiye in the period 1998-2021. The aim of the study is to examine the effects of these factors on the performance of property tax revenues and to help policymakers and tax practitioners better configure the real property tax system to bring more real estate tax revenue to the state. In the study, the method of least squares time series regression was applied. Data related to population, unemployment, inflation, and real property tax revenues were analyzed using the EViews 10 statistical program. Regression analysis indicates that there is a significant negative correlation between property tax revenues and inflation.

Keywords: Property Taxes, Local Taxes, Türkiye.

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, Türkiye'de 1998-2021 döneminde, sosyo-ekonomik faktörlerin emlak vergi gelirlerine etkisini incelemektedir. Çalışmada amaç, bu faktörlerin emlak vergi gelirlerinin performansına etkisini incelemek ve politika yapıcıların ve vergi uygulayıcılarının devlete daha fazla emlak vergi geliri getirecek şekilde emlak vergi sistemini, daha iyi yapılandırmalarına yardımcı olmaktır. Çalışmada en küçük kareler zaman serisi regresyon yöntemi uygulanmıştır. Nüfus, işsizlik ve enflasyon ile emlak vergi gelirleri ile ilgili veriler EViews 10 istatistik programı kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Regresyon analizi, emlak vergi gelirleri ile enflasyon arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı negatif bir ilişki olduğunu göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Emlak Vergileri, Yerel Vergiler, Türkiye

1. INTRODUCTION

Property taxes are taxes applied from ancient worlds such as Egypt, Babylon, Iran, and China (Carlson, 2004:3-8). Property taxation in the world is an important source of income for local governments and also an important tool that brings accountability (Bahl & Vazquez, 2007: 15). The taxation of land, land, and buildings has been done in a wide variety of ways throughout history in each country. Sometimes the number of doors, windows, chimneys, or balconies of the buildings was considered, and sometimes property rents and agricultural rent income were taxed (Arnott & Petrova, 2006: 241).

In this day and age, real estate taxation is done in three ways. Property tax; The fair market value of a property or its rental income can be calculated based on the enhanced capital value or the land value, excluding any improvements made. Although this categorization is generally adequate, it conceals the implementation of hybrid methods and system enhancements that account for particular social, economic, cultural, and financial factors. Each country applies its own tax system, considering its cultural values and political considerations (McCluskey & Williams, 2018: 12). For example, the re-evaluation periods of properties differ in each country. Some countries have a one-year, three-year, or five-year reassessment, while others have no statutory provisions regarding reassessment (Senawi et al. 2022:348).

Property tax is included in wealth tax. The common feature of wealth taxes is that individuals are held liable for their economic assets, not their economic activities. Taxes on real estate properties of real or legal persons are property taxes.

Property taxation is an intensive administrative process that includes tax base determination, assessment, calculation and collection of tax debt, taxpayer service, and resolution of disputes between the administration and taxpayers (Kelly, 2013:14). Real estate in developing countries is a financial contradiction. Because it is seen as the main source of local government revenues and its use is low in developing countries (Bahl et al. 2008:35). One of the key challenges in implementing property tax is the need for regular reassessment. Although local authorities aim to enforce property tax, the extent of their role in this policy is not always clearly understood. (Senawi et al. 2022:147).

The study examines the effect of socio-economic factors on real estate tax revenues collected by local governments in Turkey in the period of 1998-2021. Studies have been conducted on the variables that are thought to have an effect on property tax in OECD countries and South Africa. While the factors discussed in the studies affect performance in some countries, they do not in some countries. In Turkey, this issue has never been discussed. Results have contributed to the ongoing discussion among Awasthi et al. (2020), Bahl & Vazquez, (2008), Alm et al. (2011), Barako & Shibia, (2015), Hlengwai, (2019), Awasthi et al. (2020), Adjeyi et al. (2022) and others.

The remaining Chapter 2 of the study deals with the literature. Chapter 3 introduces the Turkish context. Chapter 4 describes the empirical strategy, and Chapter 5 describes the empirical analysis results and discussion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research has been carried out on real estate taxation practices and determinants of taxation around the world. De Cesare (1998) concluded in his study that public investments in urban areas often result in increased land value and benefit only a small group of private owners (Awasthi et al. 2020).

Roy W. Bahl and Jorge Martinez-Vazquez (2008) tested the variables affecting the performance of real estate tax revenues in their research in the USA with empirical analysis and discovered that the level of fiscal decentralization and advanced management plays a vital role in increasing the performance of real estate tax revenues (Bahl & Vazquez, 2008). :35-57).

James Alm, Robert D. Buschman, and David L. Sjoquist (2011) tested the factors that cause differences in property tax revenues in their research in the USA with empirical analysis and found that there are several factors that cause changes in property tax revenues, but the dominant factor is with some significant delays. They also stated that there are changes in housing prices (Alm et al. 2011: 320-331).

Sepulveda and Martinez-Vazquez (2012) conducted an empirical study on the determinants of property tax revenues in Latin American countries for the period 1990-2007 using a random effects model. From their research, they determined that there is a negative relationship between per capita income, population, and real estate tax revenues, and that transfers from the central government to local governments have a detrimental effect on the performance of real estate tax revenues (Sepulveda&Martinez-Vazquez, 2012:199-208).

Dulacha Galgalo Barako and Adan Guyo Shibia (2015) investigated the variables affecting property tax performance in Kenya. As a result of their studies, they found that urbanization, population density, and management capacity are the main factors explaining property tax performance in Kenya (Barako & Shibia, 2015: 205-214).

Samukelisiwe Hlengwai (2019) examined the effects of macroeconomic variables such as GDP rate, inflation rate, population rate, and unemployment rate on real estate tax revenues in 11 provincial municipalities in South Africa using the panel data analysis method. As a result of his study, he concluded that macroeconomic variables have a negative but significant relationship with real estate tax revenues (Hlengwai, 2019:1-100).

Rajul Awasthi, Tuan Minh Le, and Chenli You, (2020) primarily investigated the determinants of property tax revenues in the United States (USA), Australia, Canada, Chile, and later in all OECD countries using the fixed

effects model. As a result of their work; They concluded that income level, population density, and property tax rate have a significant and positive relationship with real estate tax revenue, while federal transfers and household size and real estate tax revenues have a negative relationship (Awasthi et al. 2020:1-21).

Kodzo Senyo Adjevi, Kokou Essegbe Amaglo, and Tsotsa Kouevi (2022) conducted an empirical study on the determinants of property tax in Togo and concluded that digitalization and awareness efforts positively affected the collection of property tax revenues, but land disputes were a significant barrier to the performance of property tax revenues reached (Adjevi et al. 2022).

3. TURKISH CONTEXT

Real estate tax value is taken as a basis in the regulations made in the legislation regarding expropriation, sales, barter, and rental fees of treasury real estate and some contribution amounts, as well as some other taxes and fees such as Income Tax Law, Inheritance and Gift Tax Law, Fees Law, etc. It is an important tax because it is local and widespread and the most vital source of financing that local governments need in public service provision. The ability of the real estate tax to perform the functions expected from it depends on its being high enough to be perceived by the taxpayers. The relatively weak income elasticity of the property tax and its insignificant place in tax revenues weaken the possibility of using this tax as an automatic stabilizer in cyclical periods. The fact that real estate taxation is generally applied at a single rate prevents it from playing a regulatory role in income distribution. In addition to being an objective tax, property tax is a tax that allows the application of the property principle (Şataf & Aygün, 2019:89-95).

The property tax in Turkey is a relatively recent tax that was established due to the financial reform initiatives that began during the Tanzimat era. The concept of property tax entered our tax system in 1863. This tax, which was collected by the central administration until 1985, started to be collected by local governments after this year.

Although there are 23 million real estate taxpayers in Turkey, the share of real estate tax revenues in local government revenues is quite low and insufficient. According to the law numbered 1319, although the real estate tax rates are doubled within the borders of 30 metropolitan municipalities, the share of real estate tax revenues in the budgets of the municipalities is negligible (Öz & Göker, 2016:45-46). While the share of real estate tax revenues in municipal revenues was 7.10% in 2021, its share in municipal tax revenues was 50.8% (Ministry of Treasury and Finance General Directorate of Public Accounts, 2022). One of the most important reasons why these rates are low is that the municipalities are close to the individuals living in the region and they have difficulties in going against the obliged parties due to their concerns about re-election. The number of necessary legal regulations is few and insufficient to prevent the problem (Şataf & Aygün, 2019:89-95). The most important problem in real estate tax applications is the determination of tax bases. There are significant differences between the tax values of the immovables and their market values. Many problems such as the valuation of immovables every 4 years, re-evaluation rates not reflecting the market values of immovables, insufficient number of expert appraisers and difficulties in determining building construction costs cause these differences. In a field study carried out in Ankara's Gölbaşı district in 2017, it was found that the unit prices of Treasury-owned land averaged 12.34 times the current unit values subject to real estate tax. The significant disparity between the low real estate tax value and the higher real estate sales values highlights the revenue loss in taxes and fees collected by both central and local governments from real estate transactions. (İlhan and Öz, 2020: 90). Reasons such as the high number of tax exemptions and exemptions, and the determination of tax rates far from reflecting the quality of real estate also lead to low real estate tax revenues. This decline lasted until 2016 (Şahin İpek, 2018:7-13).

Reasons such as the emergence of economic crises and the change in the method of assessing property tax also lead to low real estate tax revenues. The economic crises and the decrease in demand due to the decrease in the purchasing power of people bring stagnation in the construction sector. Economic crises, which have a greater impact on low-income people, can increase taxpayers' resistance to taxation. So much so that even conscious taxpayers can fail at the point of payment (Organ & Çiftçi, 2015: 139).

Shares of municipalities from general budget tax revenues constitute an important part of budget revenues. As of 2021, the total budget revenues of municipalities are 192,181,996 TL, and their share of general budget tax revenues is 121,947,346 TL (Ministry of Treasury and Finance General Directorate of Public Accounts, 2022).

As a result, the portion of general budget tax income in the overall revenues of municipalities stands at 48.2%. A significant drawback of this scenario is that it heightens the reliance of local governments on the central government.

While the writing system was the basis for real estate tax in Turkey until 1972, the declaration system was taken as the basis after this date. In the writing system, the taxable values of the immovables are determined ex officio by the revenue office. In the declaration system, the minimum declaration basis has been abolished. However, this basis has continued for land tax. According to the Real Estate Tax Law No. 1319, which entered into force in 1971, the real estate tax is divided into two; buildings tax and land tax. Plot tax, which is the tax on buildable land, is included in the land tax (Kurt, 2018:23). For the real estate tax, a declaration is made on the first acquisition date for the taxable building, plot and land. The declaration is not submitted unless there is a change that affects the tax later on.

The tax base values are determined by the appraisal commissions specified in Article 72 of the TPL (the mayor for the lands or an officer to be appointed as a deputy (chairman), an authorized officer from the relevant municipality, a land registry manager or an officer to be appointed as a deputy, a member elected by the chamber of commerce and the relevant neighborhood and Village headman) every 4 years and these values are updated every year with the revaluation rates determined according to the PPI (Producer Price Index) published by the Ministry of Treasury and Finance. The fair values based on the real estate tax are determined by the valuation commissions only according to their spatial characteristics (street and avenue separation). However, within the scope of the studies carried out to determine the tax value in accordance with the truth, necessary arrangements have been made in the legislation to determine the value of immovables by collective valuation methods, and this issue has been added to the duties of the General Directorate of Land Registry and Cadastre (TKGM). As of the current process, TKGM has made attempts to purchase consultancy services for the development of the collective valuation system within the scope of the real estate valuation component (İlhan and Öz, 2020: 90). The imposition, accrual, and collection authority of the property tax is left to the municipalities (Yayğır & Hacıköylü, 2018:77-93). The property tax tariff structure has been determined on a proportional basis.

Property tax rates in Turkey vary according to the nature of immovables and the status of municipalities. Property tax rates are set by the legislature. The property tax rate is applied as one per thousand for residences (2 per thousand for metropolitan municipalities), 2 per thousand for workplaces (4 per thousand for metropolitan municipalities), 3 per thousand for land (6 per thousand for metropolitan municipalities), and 1 per thousand for lands (2 per thousand for metropolitan municipalities) (Property tax law no. 1319: Articles 8 and 18).

Valuable Housing Tax was introduced with the Digital Service Tax published on 07.12.2019 and the Law on Amendments to Some Laws and the Decree-Law No. 375, and the valuable housing tax from the buildings with a building tax value of more than 5,000,000 TL determined from the residential properties located within the borders of Turkey. (Law No. 7194, Article 30 and Property Tax Law No. 1319, Article 42).

Value of residential properties subject to valuable housing tax; The ones between 6.173.000 TL and 9.260.000 TL (including this amount) for the part exceeding 6.173.000 TL (3 per thousand) and the ones up to 12,347,000 TL (including this amount) for the 9.260.000 TL 9,261 TL for its excess (6 per thousand), those with more than 12,347,000 TL are taxed at the rate of 27,783 TL for 12,347,000 TL, and 10 per thousand for the excess (General Communique of the Property Tax Law No. 80).

4. EMPIRICAL MODEL

There is a need for an in-depth understanding of the relationship between property tax revenues and socio-economic factors in local governments. Although there is a great deal of literature on property tax revenues

and taxes in general, based on OECD countries, there is no study on this subject in Turkey. The importance of this study lies in examining the impact of socio-economic factors on property tax revenues that have not been investigated in Turkey.

The main hypothesis of our empirical research is that the effect of socioeconomic factors on property tax revenues is statistically significant. Certain socio-economic indicators such as population, inflation, and unemployment were taken as independent variables, while property tax revenues were taken as dependent variables.

The factors of urbanization, corruption, and poverty could not be included in the analysis due to data insufficiency. The variables such as average household size, property tax rate, gross domestic product, and fiscal transfers from the central government to local administrations were also excluded from the analysis due to the lack of a normal time series pattern in the data. This limitation represents a fundamental constraint of the study.

4.1. Data

Data covers the period 1998 and 2021. Information on the data is given in the table below.

Table 1. Data Set (1998-2021)

Variable	Code	Source
Property Tax Revenue	LNPTR	MGM, TUIK, IMF
Population	LNPOP	TUIK, IMF
Inflation	INF	IMF
Unemployment	UE	TUIK, IMF

Property tax revenues are taken from Municipalities and Metropolitan Municipalities Budget Revenue Statistics published by the Ministry of Treasury and Finance General Directorate of Public Accounts (MGM) for the years 2006-2021 and from the IMF's World Economic Outlook Database 2022.1 Unemployment rates, inflation rates, and population data were gathered from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK) and the IMF's Word Economic Outlook Database 2022.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

The number of observations, standard deviation, minimum values, maximum values and the mean of the series of the study are as follows:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	LNPTR	LNPOP	INF	UE
Mean	14.44816	18.09647	20.68317	10.35833
Maximum	16.42925	18.25439	69.63400	14.00000
Minimum	11.48247	17.93142	6.164000	6.500000
Std. Dev.	1.460848	0.102032	20.71798	1.811057
Observations	24	24	24	24

The lines of the series give us a preliminary idea of the stagnation, trends and breaks in the series. The line graphs of the variables for the period 1998-2021 are given in Fig. 1-4.

1 All statistical information on real estate tax revenues has been confirmed by the information in the 2018-2021 Local Administrations General Activity Reports published by the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization, and Climate Change and the 2008-2017 Local Administrations General Activity Reports published by the Ministry of Interior General Directorate of Local Administrations.

LNPTR

Fig.1. Property Tax Revenues for the 1998-2021 Period

LNPOP

Fig. 2. Population Growth Rate for the 1998-2021 Period

INF

Fig. 3. Inflation rates for the 1998-2021 Period

Fig. 4. Unemployment Rates for the 1998-2021 Period

4.3. Econometric Model

This study aims to examine the effects of population, unemployment, and inflation on property tax revenue in Turkey. For this purpose, the Least Squares time series regression method was applied using the data between the 1998-2021 periods. The data was analyzed with the EViews 10 program.

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method attributed to the German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss was used in the study. It is an application method to estimate unknown parameters in the OLS regression model (Gujarati, 2022). The model established within the scope of this study is as follows:

$$LNY_t = \alpha + \beta_1 LNX1 + \beta_2 X2 + \beta_3 X3 + \varepsilon$$

LNY = Property Tax Revenue

α = Constants

β_1 - β_3 = Independent variable regression coefficient

LNX1= Population

X2 = Inflation

X3 = Unemployment

ε = Error

To minimize the variability among the values of the series related to the variables and to move the series toward stationarity, logarithmic transformations were applied to prepare the series for econometric analysis.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The stationarity of the variables is important in model estimation with the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method. In model estimations made with non-stationary series, spurious regression results can be obtained or demonstrated as if there is a non-existent relationship between the variables. For this reason, unit root tests were performed to understand whether the variables were stationary.

5.1. ADF Unit Root Test Results

In the model where variables are used, it is necessary to make sure that the variables have a unit root in order to give correct results. Augmented Dickey – Fuller (ADF) unit root test was applied for all series in the model². The findings of the test are shown in Table 3.

² ADF (Augmented Dickey-Fuller) unit root tests are used to check if a time series is constant. In these tests, the unit root hypothesis is tested by calculating the features of the time series data. The unit root hypothesis states that time is not constant and shows a trend over time. Rejection of this view indicates that the duration of time is constant and does not trend over time thereafter. In ADF unit root tests, 1st degree difference is used as a precaution for stationarity of the time series. If a time series is stationary, then the difference between values in one time interval of that time must be independent from the difference between values in another time interval. Therefore, if the time series is not stationary, first order differential retrieval is performed. This process aims to eliminate the trend in the time series in order to obtain a stationary time series. When ADF unit root tests are performed by taking first-degree difference, a stationary time series free from the influence of the trend in the time series is obtained and the number of observations decreases by 1.

Table 3. Unit Root Test Results (ADF)

$H_0: \delta = 0, t_\delta > \tau$					
$H_1: \delta < 0, t_\delta < \tau$					
At Level					
		LNPTR	LNPOP	INF	UE
With Constant	t-Statistic	-1.8296	-0.6434	-2.6868	-2.5941
	<i>P.</i>	0.3558	0.8420	0.0915	0.1091
		n0	n0	*	n0
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-2.6146	-1.8368	-1.7782	-2.8699
	<i>P.</i>	0.2777	0.6536	0.6820	0.1900
		n0	n0	n0	n0
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	2.3621	13.8738	-2.2678	0.2915
	<i>P.</i>	0.9935	1.0000	0.0254	0.7616
		n0	n0	**	n0
At First Difference					
		d(LNPTR)	d(LNPOP)	d(INF)	d(UE)
With Constant	t-Statistic	-3.7806	-4.5420	-6.5740	-4.2244
	<i>P.</i>	0.0102	0.0018	0.0000	0.0039
		**	***	***	***
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-4.3491	-4.4802	-8.6313	-4.2597
	<i>P.</i>	0.0127	0.0092	0.0000	0.0152
		**	***	***	**
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-3.2399	-0.8258	-6.5469	-4.0505
	<i>P.</i>	0.0028	0.3461	0.0000	0.0003
		***	n0	***	***

a: (*) Significant at the 10%; (**) Significant at the 5%; (***) Significant at the 1% and (no) Not Significant

b: Lag Length based on SIC

c: Probability based on MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

In Table 3, it can be noted that all variables except for INF exhibit a unit root at the level. Therefore, the series was made stationary by calculating the first difference and incorporating it into the model in this manner.

5.2. Econometric Model Estimation

As stated by Suyono et al. (2019) and Gujarati (2022), it is essential to conduct the classical assumption test prior to performing regression analysis. Therefore, classical assumption tests were applied to the model, respectively. The results of these tests are shown below.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis Results

	DLNPTR	DLNPOP	DUE	DINF
DLNPTR	1			
DLNPOP	-0.164185	1		
DUE	-0.091813	-0.052151	1	
DINF	-0.541573	-0.108761	-0.149273	1

According to the results of the correlation analysis, there is no high correlation (0.50 and above) between the independent variables. Hence, multicollinearity problem isn't expected between the independent variables.

Table 5. Variance Inflation Factors

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centered VIF
DLNPOP	100.6400	9.959951	1.016893
DUE	0.001376	1.049436	1.027765
DINF	1.29E-05	1.049601	1.037239
C	0.022089	9.954752	NA

According to the results of the variance inflation factor, VIF value is less than 10 no severe multicollinearity exists in the model.

With the normality test, it is tested whether the data to be used in the analysis are distributed or not normally distributed (Wijaya & Nugraha, 2020). Normal or near-normal distribution of the data is one of the prerequisites for the regression model. The way to detect normal or not is with Jarque-Bera.³ If probability > alpha, then the data is considered normal. But if probability < alpha, then the data is not normal (Nariswari & Nugraha, 2020).

Fig. 5. According to the Normality Test Results.

Based on the results of the Normality Test, the Jarque-Bera statistic is 3.097794 with a probability of 0.212482, which is greater than 0.05. This means that the data is normally distributed.

Table 6. Variance Test Results (Breusch-Godfrey)

F-statistic	0.296677	Prob. $F_{2,17} = 0.7471$	p > .05
Obs*R-squared	0.775700	Prob. $\chi^2_2 = 0.6785$	p > .05

According to the LM Test results⁴, the prob. values were greater than 0.05. Therefore, there is no autocorrelation in the model. The result of the White Test⁵, which was carried out to control the changing variance status, is given below.

Table 7. Heteroskedasticity Test: White

F-statistic	0.498011	Prob. $F_{9,13} = 0.8511$	p > .05
Obs*R-squared	5.896794	Prob. $\chi^2_9 = 0.7502$	p > .05

According to the results given in Table 7, the p values are not statistically significant and hence, we concluded that the variance in error terms is constant.

³ The Jarque-Bera test is a statistical hypothesis testing technique that is widely used to determine whether the data are suitable for a normal distribution. The test is named after Carlos Jarque and Anil K. Bera.

⁴ The Breusch-Godfrey test, named after Trevor S. Breusch and Leslie G. Godfrey, is an autocorrelation test applied to errors in a regression model. The Breusch-Godfrey test is sometimes called the LM test for serial correlation, as it is inspired by the idea of the Lagrange multiplier test.

⁵ The White test was developed by Halbert White (1980). The White test is general for heteroskedasticity, as it is not based on normality assumptions and is easy to implement. Therefore, it can also detect specification bias.

Table 8. Regression Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLNPOP	-13.16993	-1.312798	0.2049
DINF	-0.011640	-3.242029	0.0043
DUE	-0.039155	-1.055631	0.3044
C	0.390352	2.626428	0.0166
R-squared	0.380027		
F-statistic	3.882167		
Prob (F-statistic)	0.025465		

The R-squared value shows to what extent the independent variables explain the changes in the dependent variable. In this model, the independent variables explain approximately 38% of the changes in the dependent variable.

Prob. (F-statistic) is a statistic that shows whether the model is significant as a whole. Since the prob. (F-statistic) value is less than 0.05, the model created is significant.

There exists a statistically significant negative correlation between inflation and revenue generated from property taxes. A 1% increase in inflation creates a 0.01% decrease in property tax revenue.

The relationship between property tax revenue and inflation is with the expectations. No positive or negative statistically significant was found between the other independent variables and the dependent variable.

6. CONCLUSION

The results of the empirical analysis show that the population and unemployment rate have no effect on real estate tax revenues for Turkey, while the inflation rate has a negative significant relationship with real estate tax revenues. This confirms the Olivera-Tanzi thesis, namely that inflation has a negative effect on the real value of tax revenues. The level of inflation in the country has increased even more, especially after the Covid pandemic. This situation affects the collection of real estate tax revenues as well as all tax revenues. The negative relationship between real estate tax revenues and inflation shows that as consumer price levels increase, consumers struggle to keep up with this situation and their investment in real estate decreases. As personal income remains stagnant, rising price levels increase spending, and it becomes more costly to maintain a standard of living. It is reasonable to assume that a rise in the inflation rate frequently leads to a higher incidence of individuals failing to make their property tax payments, which subsequently diminishes the revenue generated from real estate for municipalities and, as a result, their interest income.

The lack of influence of socio-economic variables such as population and unemployment rate on property tax revenues is indicative of insufficient real estate stock in the country. High inflation and exchange rates excessively inflate housing prices, making property ownership increasingly difficult for domestic residents. Additionally, the extremely low property tax rates applied to both buildings and land negatively impact property tax revenues.

Local governments need to develop tax reforms that will increase property tax revenues. They can achieve this by updating real estate records in their jurisdictions and applying the right real estate valuation systems. Since the inflation level in the country is very high, it would be beneficial to make this valuation according to inflation indexation figures and to consider the income levels of the obliged parties. It is recommended that future researchers address the subject in terms of socio-economic variables such as the size of real estate stock at the provincial level, property prices, poverty levels, urbanization, and land ownership.

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